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Assessment of Workers Safety and Health Status in High Rise Building: A Case Project of “Double Tree by Hilton Commercial Hotel at Naxal, Kathmandu”

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Abstract

The identification of the health hazards, safety measures adopted and the measures to improve the health and safety status of the workers in the “Double Tree by Hilton” construction site were studied. The data were collected from the workers and the site management team through questionnaire survey. Data were analysed, interpreted and presented using simple descriptive statistics, tables, bar charts and pie charts using Microsoft-Excel software.

The safety and health status of workers is good as majority of the respondents revealed that there are no major and fatal accident cases are recorded at the site since construction. There is safety inspection provision by supervisor and managers at the site to determine the health hazards. But the safety meetings are occasionally held. The provision of first aid facility and medical examinations are also satisfactory. There is good provision of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) to the workers. The most essential thing like helmet are provided in adequate quantity. Safety goggles, footwear and personal fall arrest system are also available as per the requirement. Safety nets, safety signage and the management of equipment are well arranged to prevent the hazard at the site. Contract document addresses the safety provisions at the site.

It was concluded that the health and safety status of workers at construction of Double Tree by Hilton is satisfactory as the degree of injury is very low with no major and fatal injuries are recorded and the provision of safety arrangements were also done to good extent. The safety provision in the contract document was followed at the site, whereas the enforcement of Labor Act 2074 and the NBC is not concerned so far in the project. Moreover, the labor department and DUDBC inspection was also not found. Only the municipality inspects the site for safety inspection.

Keywords; Hazards, PPE, Inspection, Regulation, Contract

1. INTRODUCTION

Background

Nepal is a developing country. Most of the projects are labor intensive. The construction industry involves large skilled and unskilled workers. Any construction project has risk of accidents as they are inevitable. The safe and healthy working environment is the most important factor to be considered for a

project to be successful. There is no exact accident data recorded in Nepal. The basic problem in maintaining safe working condition in construction industries is negligence towards the safety, lack of use of proper safety equipment and tools and illiteracy in regard to the potential health hazards. In addition to that labor is unskilled, illiterate and untrained (Mishra and Sharestha, 2017)[1].

In recent years, construction of hotels, apartment, hospital buildings especially in Kathmandu Valley is growing up. Most of them are high rise buildings. High-rise buildings add more risk for workers and therefore are critical in case of workers safety because of the work is to be executed at greater heights, falling of workers and falling of materials upon worker is fatal. Slip and trip from the elevated floors, stairways due to improper housekeeping may cause fatal injuries and death. Working in deep foundation is dangerous as there is possibility of soil collapses. Using heavy machineries such as tower crane, high voltage generators, batching plant, concrete mixtures and pumps, hoists (goods lifting device) and power operated hand tools such as concrete breakers, compactors creates more risk and health hazards such as noise, dust and vibrations to workers. There is always risk of falling of workers from unguarded open edges, stair holes, lift hole and structural voids/cut outs. Difficulty in easy movement of labors in construction premises due to limited working space and insufficient logistic plan (Adhikari et al, 2020)[2].

Construction industries in Nepal have not effectively implemented safety and health measures at construction sites are found to informally stated. Due to lack of proper organizational policy, adequate resources and effective management, Nepalese construction industries are still unable to establish safe working environment at construction site.

The study is carried out at the under construction project double Tree by Hilton located at Naxal, Kathmandu. The project has designed to build two basement floor and seventeen floors above ground. The client of the project is Jagdamba Hospitality Group Pvt. Ltd, The consultant for designing of structure, architecture, finishing, MEP are international company.

Statement of the Problem

The expenditure for maintaining safety is an investment not expenditure should be understood by the involved owners, contractors and designers do care about occupational safety and health in construction site as a tendency to save money by lowering the safety standards may be risky resulting into project failure though safety pays for itself with improvement in productivity. Most of the involved workers are low experienced, low skilled and untrained, resulting increased threat of accident. Lack of effective health and safety legislations in proper monitoring and controlling mechanism of regulatory bodies as well as lack of awareness towards the safety and importance of human value are the major challenges to establish safety management system and implement comprehensive safety programs in developing countries like Nepal.

High rise building construction is new practice in Nepalese construction industries. Due to very specific nature of structure of its own, frequent operation of heavy equipment such as tower crane, hoist, concrete pumps, batching plants, engagement of large numbers of workers of various trades, various nature of works in the same construction sites, establishment of safe working environment at sites and avoiding nature of works in the same construction sites, establishing the safe working environment at sites and avoiding the ill health of workers has become more challenging as of several earlier research which need to be reconfirmed.

Accident results in loss of life, damage to the property and many injuries. Accidents and health problems bring huge cost for society, companies and individuals. However, the losses caused by accidents and ill health of workers have been either underestimated or given less preference to prevent them in the context of Nepalese construction industry as of our poor safety culture practices(Mishra and Joshi,2020)[3]. Furthermore, enforcement of existing laws, acts and regulations relating to health and safety of workers is very weak due to the lack of strict monitoring by concerned authorities. Health and safety trainings which contributed to develop safety awareness among workers and supervisors are inadequate. Therefore, it seems to be of prime importance, at present to carry out effective safety precaution measures and policies in compliance with state rules and regulations at construction sites to minimize economic, social and legal losses caused by accidents and ill health. It is highly relevant to carry out the study on health and safety status of workers in construction of Double Tree by Hilton, Naxal, Kathmandu.

Research Objectives

The general objective of this research is to assess the occupational safety and health status of workers in terms of hazards and precaution measures in high rise commercial building construction site in Kathmandu valley.

LITERATURE REVIEW

High-rise Building Construction in Nepal

The real state and housing business has become one of the sectors having significant investments. According to real-estate developers, the sector currently has an investment of around 200 billion.

Table 1 Status of High Rise Building in Kathmandu Valley

S/N	Particulars	Numbers			
1	On OperationalPhasewithCompletionCertificate	17			
2	OnConstructionPhaseand others	53			
	Total	70			
S/N	Particulars	Kathmandu	Lalitpur	Bhaktapur	Total
1	No. of Building	49	21	1	71

Table 1. District wise distribution of High Rise Building in Kathmandu[*Source: Mishra et al., 2021 and Mishra and Aithal,2021*][4&5]

Need for Occupational safety and Health Provision in construction site:

The contractors are not properly trained and they wrongly believe that they can save money by lowering safety standard. In Nepal the worker are un-organized and not trained properly. Workers work as seasonal they mainly focus on agriculture based economy. And when they become free from agricultural work then they join the construction work as a seasonal worker. Hence Safety on construction site is needed more in Nepal than other country. In construction industry, most of accidents can be predicted before they occur, hence they can be prevented. Construction is basic activity for development of Nation. Also the rate of accident can be minimized if adequate attention is given for safety in construction. We should believe without any doubt that the safety is needed to minimize rate of accident, raise morale of construction workers, increase efficiency of works, improve quality of works, overcome the issue of fatal accident and minimize construction cost.

Benefits of Safety and Health Provision

Source: Mishra et al, 2021 ,20& 19[6,7 &8]

Figure 1Benefit of Safety and Health Provision

Situation of Implementation of OSH in Nepal

The poor implementation of safety provisions and regulations ensured by state laws and acts at site due to lack of proper safety policy and plan, separate safety department with safety manager and adequate budget is observed in the construction sites that are leading to the major casualties. The major fatalities in high rise building construction are caused by fall from heights. The unprotected edges of floors and roofs are the prominent source of fall. The dust is the prominent hazard causing ill health of workers. And most prominent sources of dust hazards are construction materials such as sand and cement to which workers are exposed daily. There are various contributing factors of injuries and fatalities at project sites. Lack of regular safety inspection, failure to use personal protective equipment (PPE) in working site, lack of conducting safety training and safety meeting among workers are the key contributing factors of occupational fatalities and injuries. It was found from field survey that key safety protection measures are not made available at site. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) are not available at all sites appropriately and adequately. Only hard hats and safety belts are available more frequently in almost sites. First aid box, emergency vehicles and fire protection systems are not satisfactorily available. Use of proper informatory and caution signs and signal, guardrails and barriers in hazardous area and machineries which are prime safety precaution measures are either not provided or poorly implemented at sites under study. The poor implementation is also contributed by lack of regular safety inspection by government authorities and mandatory provisions of fines and other punitive measures if one does not follow safety acts and regulations(Mishra and Sharestha, 2017) [1].

The enforcement of the Labor Act and Labor Regulation is weak in the construction sites. The lack of safety inspection and monitoring from the government is responsible for the lacking implementation of act and regulation leading to the poor OSH status of the workers. The site specific safety policy and plan is the requirement to avoid the weak implementation status of the acts and regulations that impact the OSH status. The safe and healthy work environment can be achieved only after the realization and practice the measures by all major stakeholders i.e. the government, contractor and workers (Mishra and Sharestha , 2017)[1]

Many occupational accidents are accompanied by stepping on the sharp or pointed objects, slip, as well as cut and scratch. The study found that traditional working method, improper framework, lack of training, lack of accountability, improper material handling and inadequacy of personal protective equipment were various causes of accident at workplace. Both contractors and workers were found neglecting safe procedures on site. There weren't any safety plan and appointed safety officer on site for safety inspection. It was found out that there was no any provision of safety budget and safety audit; no any arrangement of safety meeting and training, and very less attention were given towards using various systems to control unsafe condition on site. Despite the lack of medical examination facility, provision of first aid facility had been partially full filled in project sites.

The Act Regulation maintained and implemented by Department of Labor are Child Labor (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 2056 (2000), The Labor Act, (1992) , The Labor Act 2074, Bonus Act, 2030 (1973), Trade Union Act, Labor Regulations ,2075, Trade Union Regulations, 2049, Bonus Regulations, 2039, Immigration Rules, 2051;

Directories – Policy and Foreign Employment Policy 2068.

It is to be provided from the insurance amount, Disability Compensation:

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Employee or worker shall be paid from an insurance amount on the basis of degree of disability. Death Compensation: The nearest successor is entitled to the amount of accident insurance as per the new act in case of death of the worker. Medical Insurance Coverage: At least 1 Lakh per year for every worker. Premium to be paid equally by the employer and worker. Accident Insurance Coverage: At least 7 Lakh for every worker. Premium to be paid fully by the employer.
(NBSM, 2017)

Prevention and Control Measures

There are the following contributing preventive measures or factors to maintain the better safety at workplace such as Company Safety policy, Safety awareness program, Safety training, Safety Meeting & toolbox talk, Proper uses of personal protective equipment (PPE) and uniform, Establishment of safety department, Assigning safety engineer/officer and inspection, Guard rail & barrier for open space, Signage, signals, lighting and instruction notice, First aid kit, first aid box and first aid rooms, Good material handling and storage, Safety award, Third party inspection for equipment & temporary structures, Preventive maintenance, Emergency planning, Sufficient safety budget and Adequate working space, accommodation and foods.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research design:

The flow chart diagram of the methodology is shown figure 2:

Figure 2: Research Flow Chart

This is a pragmatic research with both inductive and deductive logical reasoning field based study. The research was designed to extract relevant information from workers and management team. Besides this, the past studies concerning the occupational health and safety hazards were reviewed in detail. Methodology for the thesis was found with such studies and series of informal meetings, discussions with concerned authorities and workers.

Study Area

The research was conducted on a commercial hotel, Double Tree, building construction site located in Naxal, Kathmandu. The table 2 shows the brief of hotel building under study:

It is an under construction Five Star Hotel for the tourist attraction and is projected to be the largest and the most lavishing modern Hotel with total floor area of 170,000 sq. feet having 176 number of room keys situated at Naxal. The project is the fusion of modern architecture and modern amenities of every kind.

Table 2 Project Title

Project Name:	Double Tree by Hilton
Location	Naxal, Kathmandu

Date of start	May, 2016
Date of Completion	Dec, 2019
Number of Storey	2B+G+16
Built up Area	31,000 sq. ft.
Name of Employer	Jagdamba Hospitality Group Pvt. Ltd.
Name of Contractor	Roshan Construction Pvt.Ltd.

Study Population, Samples Selection and Sample Size:

The workers and the site management of the under construction project is target source of primary data. Total numbers of the workers in each construction site were located. The sample selections of the workers was based on random sampling method and sample size is selected based on Cochran’s formula. Similarly, the sample selection of site management was also based on purposive sampling method and one representative of contractor, one of client (developer) and one of engineers were interviewed.

Cochran’s Formula:

$$n_0 = Z^2 pq / e^2$$

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \frac{n_0 - 1}{N}}$$

Where,

n = sample size, Z = 1.64 (at 90% confidence level), p = sample proportion (0.5)

N = population size, e = Level of precision (=/- 10%)

n₀ = calculated sample size

Table 3 Population size, Sample size and Sample selection method

S.N.	Respondents	Population size (Nos.) N	Calculated sample size (Nos.)	Sample size (Nos.) n	Sampling method
1	Workers	150	47	85	Purposive sampling
2	Site management team	25	18	22	Purposive sampling

Collection of Secondary Data and Information

The secondary data was collected from different sources. These includes safety related books, journals, articles, papers, thesis reports, booklets, websites etc. Apart from this, the informal discussion with engineers, supervisors and workers working in the construction companies, consultancies, clients and contractors was taken as valuable assets for the study.

Primary Data Collection

Mainly, primary data was collected by questionnaire method. A structured and closed-ended (Yes/No) questionnaire was prepared to collect primary data regarding safety provision according to the Nepalese Legislation, its implementation, workers awareness towards safety and appropriate safety measures on construction sites, types of occupational hazards occurring at the sites, their causes and other required queries so as to fulfill the objectives. The questionnaires were directly be distributed to prospective respondents by the researcher and brief interview and necessary queries was conducted. Site inspection was conducted adequately and photographs of sites under study were taken. The respondents were as follows:

- Site Management Team
 - Contractors
 - Engineers
 - Supervisor
- Individual workers
- Field Observation

Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaires survey were analyzed using Microsoft Excel software. Since the Study is descriptive study, simple frequency distributions were used as analytical tool. Data were analyzed, interpreted and presented using simple descriptive statistics, tables' bar charts and pie chart.

4. Results and Discussion

Occupational Safety and Health Hazards with Causes

The different types of hazards occurring in the study site, their causes and the safety provisions available at the construction sites are studied with through the questionnaire survey with workers and the site management team.

Major type of hazard prevailed in the construction site

It shows the result on major hazard prevailed in the construction site. 35% of workers responded the major hazard to be the mechanical hazard, while 41% of site management team responded it to be the major hazard prevailed in the construction site. The second major hazard is physical hazard. 36% of site management team and 29% of workers responded the physical hazard is second highest occurring hazard. The third highest occurring hazard is chemical followed by psychosocial hazard.

In my observation I found that there is large number of plant and equipment to be used while working so the mechanical hazard is the most prevailed hazard in the site.

It reveal about the cases of accidents in the construction site. 61% of workers and 86% of site management team revealed that there are cases of accidents in the site while 29% of workers and 14% of site management team said that there are no cases of accidents in the site. 9% of workers are unknown about the cases of accidents.

Degree of injury

The table 4 show the degree of injury occurred in the construction site according to the workers and the Site management team.

Table 4 Degree of injury in the construction site

Responses	No. of workers	Percentage (%)	No. of Site management team	Percentage (%)
Minor	52	100%	19	100
Major	0	0	0	0
Fatal	0	0	0	0
Total	52	0	19	100

The total 85 of the workers were surveyed among which 52 revealed that there are cases of accident in the sites. After asking them about the degree of the accident, all 52 of them said that the accident was of minor type. Similarly, among the total 22 of the surveyed site management team, 19 revealed that there are cases of accidents in the site and all of them said that the degree of injury in the occurred accident cases are minor.

Though the accidents occur in the sites, the degree of the case is minor. No fatal and major accidents are occurred. So those minor accidents can be easily minimized after the identification of causes and working on those.

Most common physical hazard at the site

The results on the most common type of physical hazard at the site. 52% of workers responded that noise is the major physical hazard at the site. 29% believed the poor light to be the common physical hazard. 12% responded heat stress and 7% responded electrical shock.

Most Common Mechanical Hazard which causes Accidents at the Site

The figure 4.4 shows the most common mechanical hazards which cause accidents at the site. 66% responded that the most of the accidents in the site is caused by struck by the objects. 28% of the respondent workers revealed that the accidents are caused at the site due to fall hazard. 6% think that the accident is caused by caught in between equipment and nobody responded on collision.

Common Source of Fall Hazard

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It shows that 44% of the workers revealed that fall hazard is caused due to slip, trip and fall from the stairways. 23% said that unguarded openings in floor and roof structures cause fall hazards. 21% think it is due to unprotected edges and 12% think it is due to scaffold.

Common Source of “struck by objects” Fatalities

The results on common source of “struck by objects” fatalities are 61% of the workers responded that falling objects are the most common source of the struck by object fatalities while 39% responded that the equipment are the source of struck by objects fatalities.

Nobody think flying objects are the source of such fatalities.

In my view the struck by objects being the most common hazard occurring in the site, the activities should be carried out more carefully and it should be made sure that every worker is compulsorily provided with the helmets and workers wear it during the site.

Common Source of “Caught in between objects” Fatalities

It shows the common source of “caught in between object” fatalities. 54% of the respondents revealed that machinery/mechanical equipment are the major source of “caught in between objects” fatalities. 32% reveal the source to be framework collapse and 14% said structural member collapse is the source of the accidents caused due to “caught in between objects”.

Cause of Exposure to Electrical Shock

It shows the results of causes of electrical shock. 55% of the workers said that live circuit causes the electrical shock. 39% shared that power lines causes the electrical shock and 6% revealed that power tools are responsible for electrical shock.

Common Source of Noise & Vibration

It shows the common sources of noise and vibration as responded by workers. 68% of workers responded that hand-held power tools such as concrete breaker, vibrator, disc grinder etc. are the most common sources of noise and vibration. 15% said the concrete pump produce noise and vibration. 11% said excavator and 6% said generator cause the noise and vibration at the site.

Common Chemical Hazard at the Site

It show that the most common source of chemical hazard at the site is dust followed by welding fumes, gases and acid. Since the construction is going on, the paint has not been reported as a source of chemical hazard.

Common Source of Dust Generation

The most common source of dust hazard is handling of cement. 81% respondents revealed that cement works generate dust. 11% said that cutting and abrasion work cause dust. 6% said that metal welding and cutting work causes dust and 2% said that marble grinding work generate dust.

Cement works are the major source of dust in the building construction site. Most of the people suffer from problems related to throat and lung in case of long exposure to cement dust.

Common Risk due to Chemical Hazard

The common risk of chemical hazards are 66% of workers revealed that allergies are commonly caused due to prevalent chemical hazard. 20 % revealed skin burn, 14% revealed irritation and nobody talked about asthma.

Most Prevalent Psychosocial Hazard at the Construction Site

It shows the prevalent psychosocial hazard at the construction site. 33% workers and 41% site management team revealed that overtime work among the workers is the most prevalent psychosocial hazard at the site. 29% of workers marked wages and leave, 26% marked job insecurity, 8% said job dissatisfaction and 4% said alcoholism as the prevalent psychosocial hazards. While according to site management team, after the overtime work, 23% of the team said job satisfaction as the prevalent psychosocial hazard, 18% said alcoholism among workers, 2% said wages and leave and also 2% said job insecurity as the psychosocial hazard.

Safety Supervisor/Manager Inspection at Site

It represents the status of safety inspection by supervisor and managers. 71% of workers revealed that there is safety inspection by supervisor and managers regularly at the site to determine the health hazards. 5% of the workers said that there is no inspection and 25% said inspection is carried out sometimes. 68% of the site management team responded that there is safety inspection of supervisor and manager to determine health hazards in the site. 14% revealed there is no inspection and 18% revealed sometimes the inspection is carried out with the aim of determining hazards.

Safety Meetings at Site to Communicate Safety Information

It reveals that 82% of the workers responded that the safety meetings are occasionally held on the site to communicate safety information, 15 % responded that the meetings are frequently held and 2% of workers responded that the meetings are never held. While the site management team responded that, 64% of them said meetings are occasionally held, 36% said frequently held and nobody from the site management team said that it is never performed. The table 5 shows the frequency of safety meetings conducted at site.

Table5 Frequency of safety meetings at site

Responses	No. of Workers	Percentage (%)	No. of Site management team	Percentage (%)
Frequently	13	15.29	8	36.36
Occasionally	70	82.35	14	63.63
Never	2	2.35	0	0
Total	85	100	22	100

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First Aid Facilities made available at the Site

The responses on the status of first aid facility available at the site shows, all the interviewed workers and the employer team stated that the first aid facility is available at their site.

Medical Examinations Conducted at the Site

Both the worker and the site management team were interviewed to obtain the results. 50% of the site management team revealed that the medical examinations are conducted at the site monthly. 36% of the team said that it is conducted in every six months, 2% said yearly and 5% said that it is conducted once in a project.

Whereas, the 39% workers responded that the medical examinations of the workers are conducted monthly, 20% in every six months, 15% in yearly, 19% said once in a project and 7% said it is never conducted.

Figure 3: Occupational Safety and Health Hazards and their Causes

Safety Precaution Measures & Improvements Required

Management Provide following PPE at your Construction Project

It shows the status of provision of PPE at the construction project as responded by the workers. 100% of the workers said they are always provided with safety helmets. 88% responded that they are always provided with safety goggles and 12% responded that they are sometimes provided safety goggles.

Likewise regarding safety footwear, 12% responded that they are always provided safety footwear, 67% responded that they are sometimes provided safety footwear and 21% responded that they are never provided with safety footwear.

Regarding personal fall arrest system, 22% of the workers responded that they are always provided with it, 65% said they are sometimes provided and 13% said that they are never provided with the personal fall arrest system.

Supervisor use Safety Checklists before Starting Work

It shows that 56% of the respondents reveal that supervisors use the safety checklist before starting work and 46% said that the supervisors do not check the safety checklist before starting work.

Management provided the Horizontal Safety Nets at the Construction Site

The 61% of the workers said that there is provision of safety nets at the construction site and 39% said that there is sometimes the provision of the safety nets.

It shows the areas where safety nets are placed. The 58% of the workers responded that the safety nets are placed on the perimeter of structure, 16% of them responded that the safety nets are placed only on the interior of structures and 14% said that the safety nets are placed on the both perimeter and the interior of the structures.

Practice of Display Safety Signage in the Hazardous Area at Site

All the 85 workers responded that there is safety signage in the site in the required areas.

Management of Guardrails and Barriers on Structural Openings, Open Edges, moving Machinery and other Hazardous Area by Contractor to prevent access of Workers

It reveal that 84% of the respondents said that the contractor has managed the guardrails and barriers on the structural openings, open edges, moving machinery and other hazardous area to prevent access of workers.

The 16% of the workers responded that the contractor has partially managed the guardrails and barriers on the structural openings, open edges, moving machinery and other hazardous area to prevent access of workers.

Measures Adopted for Better Safety and Health in Construction Site

The summarizes result on measures adopted for better safety and health in construction site. 58% of workers revealed that providing sufficient PPE is adopted as safety and health measure in the construction site. 16% said that providing safety training is adopted, 19% said that replacement of faulty equipment is done and 7% said the appointment of safety supervisors is adopted as safety and health measure.

Whereas, when interviewed with site management team, 55% of the team responded that providing sufficient PPE is adopted as the safety and health measure. 23% responded that providing safety training is adopted, 14% revealed that appointment of safety supervisor is adopted and 9% said that replacement of faulty equipment is done as a safety and health measure.

Figure 4: Safety Precaution Measures & Improvements Requirement

Safety Laws, Policies and their Implementation

Availability of Documented Safety Policy in the Project

The site management team when interviewed, all 22 of them revealed that there is documented policy in the project. The whole interviewed site management team responded that there is implementation of specific safety plan at the site.

Act/Regulation that Address the Safety of Workers at Construction Site

It represent that safety provision in contract document addresses the safety at the construction site. The labor act and NBC is not usually followed. It summarizes that 68% of the respondents from the site management team revealed that no safety inspections are done form the government side. While 14% said there is regular safety inspection and 18% revealed that there is safety inspection only sometimes.

It shows that municipality inspects the construction site for safety inspection.

The two important authorities who had to be concerned about the safety and health regulation in the construction sites was found to be very inactive in terms of inspection. In my view, this is a serious problem.

Safety and health measure compulsory adoption in contract Document

It shows that the safety and health measures are compulsorily adopted in the contract document according to the site management team.

Figure 5 :Safety Laws, Policies and their Implementation

The safety and health provisions were followed solely depending upon the clauses of contract documents.

CONCLUSION

it is observed that 35% workers and 41% Site management team responded that mechanical hazard is the major hazard prevailed in the construction site was no fatal and major accidents occurred in site. After the mechanical hazard, physical hazard is most occurring hazard, where noise is most common problem followed by poor light, heat stress and electric shock respectively where struck by objects is most common hazard followed by fall hazard and caught in between equipment causes of struck by objects are falling objects and equipment the fall hazards are strip, trip and fall from stairways, unguarded openings in floor and roof structures, unprotected edges and scaffold respectively.

28% of the workers and 23% Site management team responded that the chemical hazard is the major hazard prevailed in the site, where dust is the prominent cause of the hazard. Other causes are welding fumes, gases and acids respectively. Workers believed that psychosocial hazard is major hazard in the site with causes like overtime work, wages and leave, job insecurity, job dissatisfaction and alcoholism respectively. However, the Site management teams do not think psychosocial hazard is the major problem, but they think the hazard might have prevailed due to overtime work, job dissatisfaction, and alcoholism, wages and leave and job insecurity respectively. Most of the workers (71%) revealed that there is safety inspection by supervisor and managers regularly at the site to determine the health hazards. Also most of the Site management team (68%) responded that there is safety inspection of supervisor and manager to determine health hazards in the site whereas, safety meetings are found to be occasionally held in the site. There is availability of first aid facility at the site. Most of the workers (39%) and Site

management team (50%) said that the medical examinations are conducted monthly in the sitewhile others experienced the service in every six months, once in a year and once in the project respectively.

Provision of PPE is also satisfactory. The most important equipment like helmets are available in adequate quantity. Safety goggles, footwear and personal fall arrest system are also available as per the requirement. Safety nets, safety signage and the management of equipment are well arranged to prevent the hazard at the site. Majority of workers and Site management team revealed that provision of sufficient PPE is the most adopted safety and health measure in the construction site. Workers (19%) believed that the faulty equipment are replaced and 16% of them thought safety training is adopted while very few i.e. 7% said that appointment of safety supervisor is done as a safety and health measure to prevent the hazards. Whereas most of the Site management team (55%) shared that there is provision of sufficient PPE adopted as safety and health measure. Safety trainings, appointment of safety supervisor and replacement of faulty equipment are respectively adopted as safety and health measure according to the Site management team. Safety provision in contract document addresses the safety at the construction site. The safety and health measures are compulsorily adopted in the contract document according to the site management team. 68% of the respondents from the site management team revealed that no safety inspections are done from the government side. While 14% said there is regular safety inspection and 18% revealed that there is safety inspection only sometimes. The municipality inspects the construction site for safety inspection. Neither the labor department nor the DUDBC inspect the site.

From the study it was concluded that the health and safety status of workers at construction of Double Tree by Hilton is satisfactory as the degree of injury is very low with no major and fatal injuries are recorded and the provision of safety arrangements were also done to good extent. However the regular inspection of supervisor at site, use of safety checklist regularly, medical examinations of every worker in proper time period and accordingly allocating them the works should be made more effective. The safety provision in the contract document was followed at the site, whereas the enforcement of labor act 2074 and the NBC is not concerned so far in the project. Moreover, the labor department and DUDBC inspection was also not found. Only the municipality inspects the site for safety inspection.

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